

Electric Fencing For Silvopastoral Management in Mountain Landscapes

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Electric fence installation

Electric and mobile fencing is especially well-suited for silvopastoral management, as it supports both herd mobility in mountainous landscapes and the conservation of wildlife in high natural value areas such as the Montesinho Natural Park.

Its advantages include the farmer's freedom to carry out other agricultural activities and the possibility of exploiting a larger forage area. Compared to fixed and permanent fences, electric fences offer greater flexibility and lower investment costs. However, mobile versions require more labour to assemble and dismantle, as well as periodic checks to ensure they are working properly. Electric fences are also a tool to help protect livestock from predators and safeguard crops from attacks by wildlife (such as deer and wild boar). They are also useful for fertilizing farmland, keeping animals safe while they nap during the hottest hours, and allowing greater freedom in grazing and farm management. There are different types of fences and materials, which vary depending on their purpose, whether it's to contain animals or ward off predators. Electric fences require an earth connection and are made up of electrifiers (powered by a battery, electricity grid or solar panel), posts (fiberglass, plastic or iron), conductors (wires or tapes) and insulators. Choosing the right system depends on factors such as the length of the fence, the relief of the terrain, dense vegetation and soil characteristics such as composition and humidity, which can affect electrical conduction, requiring more powerful or additional systems to ensure efficiency.

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